

Pest Control and Management

DISEASES

Seed treatment against tungro (RTV)

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We evaluated five levels of furathiocarb (Promet 40 SD) for seed treatment against RTV in Maros and Lanrang, South Sulawesi. Seed was submerged 24 h and air-dried 10 min, then mixed with furathiocarb powder. Seeds were planted 24 h after treatment in 2- × 4-m seedbeds.

Green leafhopper (GLH) populations were estimated by covering each hill once a week to 4 wk after sowing (WAS) with a 20- × 20- × 30-cm transparent mylar cage and counting GLH in the cage. Ten cages per seedbed were used with 3 replications.

In Maros, GLH population and RTV

Effect of seed treatment on GLH population and RTV incidence in South Sulawesi, Indonesia.

Treatment (g furathiocarb/kg seed)	GLH/hill (WAS)				RTV incidence (%)
	1 wk	2 wk	3 wk	4 wk	
	<i>Maros</i>				
10	0.2	0.7	0.8	0.7	0.5
15	0.0	0.4	0.6	0.9	0.4
20	0.0	1.2	0.9	0.8	0.2
25	0.2	0.9	0.4	1.4	0.2
40	0.3	1.1	1.2	1.4	0.0
Control	0.1	1.0	1.3	2.0	1.3
	<i>Lanrang</i> ^a				
10	13 abc	25 a	17 ab	13 ab	65
15	17 bc	24 a	17 ab	15 bc	81
20	10 ab	23 a	13 ab	11 ab	77
25	13 abc	24 a	13 a	9 ab	26
40	8 a	22 a	11 a	7 a	20
Control	20 c	32 a	26 b	22 c	88

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter do not significantly differ at the 5% level (DMRT).

incidence were low even 7 WAS (see table). Although GLH populations were quite high in Lanrang, RTV infection did not appear until 4 WAS. Incidence

was 20-90% 7 WAS. Furathiocarb at 25 and 40 g/kg seeds provided the best control in Lanrang. □

Heat and chemical therapy to eradicate *Pseudomonas fuscovaginatae* from rice seed

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Seedborne and seed-transmitted fluorescent *Pseudomonas* spp. have been shown to cause sheath rot, and grain discoloration and sterility in Japan, southern Europe, Africa, and Latin America. The pathogens have been identified as *P. syringae* pv. *syringae*, *P. fuscovaginatae* (= *P. marginalis* = *P. fluorescens* biovar II), but the taxonomy is unclear.

National quarantine norms often require that imported seed be free of seed-transmitted pathogens. We undertook studies to evaluate chemical seed treatment and heat therapy for eradicating pathogens from rice seed.

Dry heat is known to eradicate *P. fuscovaginatae* from seed, but the long-term effect on seed viability is not known. Hot water therapy (55°C, 20 min) to eradicate *Aphelenchoides besseyi* from seed is a common practice. Tetracycline is known to reduce *P. fuscovaginatae* infection, but agricultural chemicals registered for rice have not been tested.

Kasugamycin, propineb, captan, mancozeb, edifenphos, tricyclazone, benomyl, and captafol, which are commonly used in Latin America to control grain discoloration and neck blast, were prescreened for ability to limit *in vitro* colony growth of isolates from Latin America, Asia, and Africa. Only kasugamycin showed a significant negative effect on colony growth of *P. fuscovaginatae*, and none had a significant effect on *P. syringae* pv. *syringae* or *P. avenae* (nonfluorescent). Therefore, dry heat and hot water were compared with kasugamycin at 0.2 g ai/kg seed for

their efficiencies in eradicating the pathogens. Test seed was harvested from plants inoculated with Latin American isolates of *P. fuscovaginatae*.

The two heat therapies were completely effective (Table 1). Kasugamycin significantly reduced but did not eradicate the pathogen.

We assessed the effect of dry heat

Table 1. Comparison of heat^a and antibiotic treatments for eradicating *Pseudomonas fuscovaginatae* from rice seed.^b Cali, Colombia, 1987.

Isolate	Contamination (%)	
	Untreated	Kasugamycin at 0.2 g ai/kg seed
BCE-3	33	4.0
BCE-23	31.9	0
532	28	2.9

^aThe heat treatments (65°C for 6 d, or 55°C water for 20 min) produced no contamination. ^bSeed from plants inoculated at booting with pathogenic isolates of *P. fuscovaginatae*. Mean of 2 replications, 100 seeds each. All treatments had significantly lower contamination than the untreated for the 3 isolates.